

ROLE OF HRM PRACTICES ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN NEPALESE PUBLIC FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS: TEST OF MEDIATING EFFECT OF OCB

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Abstract

The objective of the study was to examine the impact of HRM practices on organizational performance (OP) with an analysis of the mediating effect of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in Nepalese public financial institutions. A quantitative research approach and a casual comparative research design have been used in the study. The sample size has been 480 respondents, out of which 472 usable respondents have been received. Structural equation modeling (SEM) has been used to analyze the direct and mediating effects. The study's findings revealed that HRM practices had a positive and significant impact on organizational performance. OCB partially mediated the relationship between HRM practices and organizational performance in Nepalese public financial institutions. OCB is a prominent factor in Nepalese public financial institutions that strengthens the link between HRM practices and organizational performance.

Keywords: HRM Practices, OCB, Organizational Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

HRM practices can produce the knowledge, motivation, synergy, and commitment of a management's employees to develop a source of sustained competitive advantage for the management (Harter et al., 2002). HRM practices (Basnet et al., 2024) were defined as selection, empowerment, training and development, communication, performance appraisal, and performance-related reward in the Nepalese public financial sectors. Organizational performance is an indicator that measures the organization's ability to achieve organizational goals (Ho, 2011). HRM practices in the organization can improve organizational performance (Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013; Amin et al., 2014; Farouk et al., 2016; Taamneh et al., 2018; Jaiswal & Kumar, 2020; Ali et al., 2020; Islami, 2021). Organizational citizenship behavior plays a necessary role in increasing the association between HRM practices and organizational performance (Sun et al., 2007; Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013; Taamneh et al., 2018). OCB plays a role in the relationship between HRMP and intellectual capital (Khan et al., 2023). Organizational performance can be enhanced by HRM practices performance in the manufacturing and service sectors in Nepal

(Pradhan, 2019). HRM practices improve organizational commitment through person-organization fit in the Nepali banking sector (Suryanarayana, 2022). However, the prior studies did not use the mediating effect of OCB on the association between HRM practices and organizational performance. Therefore, this study examines the relationship between HRM practices and organizational performance through the mediating effect of OCB in Nepalese public financial institutions.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Theoretical Review

The universalistic perspective (Delery & Doty, 1996) proclaims that certain management practices are universally applicable and lead to superior performance outcomes. The best practice is a set of HRMP that are universal in the sense that they are best in any situation, which will lead to superior OP (Delery & Doty, 1996; Pfeffer, 1998; Armstrong & Taylor, 2014). Thus, the universalistic perspective is the best HRMP that all the institutions are implying proper HRM practices to enrich the OP. Social exchange theory (SET) (Blau, 1964) is a sociological and psychological framework that expounds social relationships as a series of exchanges where individuals aim to maximize benefits and minimize costs. Positive SET (Blau, 1964) can mutually benefit the employing organization and the workforce (Gould-Williams & Davies, 2005). Positive SET (Blau, 1964) suggested that the relationship between HRM practices and organizational performance may be mediated by employees' work attitudes (such as OCB) (Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013).

Empirical Review

HRM Practices and Organizational Performance

Human resource management practices refer to the strategies, policies, and actions employed by organizations to manage their workforce effectively (Boxall & Purcell, 2016). OP is the competency of the organization to obtain the organization's objectives (Ricardo & Wade, 2001). HRM practices positively and significantly impacted perceived organizational performance (Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013; Amin et al., 2014; Farouk et al., 2016; Taamneh et al., 2018; Jaiswal & Kumar, 2020; Ali et al., 2020; Islami, 2021). HRM practices had an insignificant effect on organizational performance (Nawal et al., 2021). The second hypothesis was formulated based on literature and a universalistic perspective.

H_1 : HRM practices have a positive influence on organizational performance.

The Association Between HRM Practices and Organizational Performance Mediated by OCB

HRM practices encompass the deliberate policies and systems designed to invite, improve, inspire, and maintain employees, ensuring their alignment with organizational goals (Armstrong, 2020). OP is determined by organizational effectiveness and efficiency to attain objectives (Stoner et al., 1995). OCB describes people's extra-role activities that aren't recognized by a formal workplace incentive system (Podsakoff & MacKenzie,

1994). The association between organizational performance and high-performance HR practices was mediated by OCB (Sun et al., 2007). Organizational performance and HRM practices were mediated by OCB (Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013; Taamneh et al., 2018). Moreover, OCB partially mediated the relationship between HRM practices and organizational performance (Taamneh et al., 2018). OCB partially mediated the relationship between HRMP and intellectual capital (Khan et al., 2023). The second hypothesis was projected with the help of literature and positive social exchange theory.

H_2 : The association between HRM practices and organizational performance is mediated by organizational citizenship behavior

3. CONCEPTUAL FORMWORK

Source: Taamneh et al. (2018), Ko and Smith-Walter (2013)

Figure 1: Conceptual Formwork of the study

4. METHODOLOGY

The quantitative research approach and causal-comparative research design have been used in this study. Cronbach's alpha was used to test the reliability of variables and related questions. CFA was used to test the validity of the constructs. Frequency distribution has been applied to identify the respondents' profiles. SEM has been used to explore the impact of HRM practices on organizational performance. SEM has been applied to explain the mediating effect of OCB on the association between HRM practices and organizational performance. The primary data has been used. The population has considered 2,251 officer-level employees of Nepalese public financial institutions (Ministry of Finance, 2079). As a general rule, the sample size should be at least ten times the number of observations per variable (Hair et al., 2019). In this study, eight constructs have been measured using 48 items. Therefore, the sample size has been 480. Purposive sampling has been applied to select respondents. Out of the total 480 questionnaires distributed to officer-level employees within the Nepalese public financial institutions in a

personal way, 475 questionnaires were returned. Out of the 475 questionnaires returned, only 472 questionnaires were usable. Thus, 472 usable questionnaires have been used for the study.

Measurement Scale and Cronbach 'Alpha of Variables -Related Questions

Selection, training and development, performance evaluation, performance-related rewards, communication, and empowerment were used to gauge HRM practices (Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013; Taamneh et al., 2018). Selection was measured by “need assessment is made before recruitment in my organization (0.892),” “preliminary screening is undertaken before selecting candidates (0.899),” “selection criteria are developed before taking exam for selection (0.884),” “job-related knowledge test is emphasized while selecting employees (0.872),” and “work experience is one of the major criteria while selecting employees (0.874)” (Tsaur & Lin, 2004; Wei et al., 2010; Moideenkutty et al., 2011). Training and development was measured through “training needs survey is undertaken to determine the needs of training (0.889),” “training and development programs are regular phenomena of my organization (0.895),” “organization encourages employees to participate in training and development activities (0.891),” “sometimes training and development programs are organized outside the workplace (0.907),” and “the effectiveness of the training program is measured based on the change in the behavior of employees (0.901)” (Tsaur & Lin, 2004; Wei et al., 2010; Al Damoe et al., 2017).

Performance appraisal was evaluated through “performance appraisal committee appraises the work performance of the employees (0.855),” “performance appraisal report is discussed among the superior and the employees (0.871),” “performance appraisal supports employee career paths (0.879),” and “employees’ performance appraisal is made by the immediate supervisor (0.887).” (Whiting et al., 2008; Hashim, 2010). Performance-related reward was measured using “employees are provided paid holiday based on their performance (0.882),” “wage is determined based on performance (0.900),” “employees are given cash incentive based on their performance (0.899),” “employees are provided transportation facilities based on their performance (0.898),” and “employees are promoted based on their performance (0.905).” (Wei et al., 2010; Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013). Communication was measured by “a clear communication structure is defined by the structure (0.879),” “a formal channel of communication is used within the organization (0.826),” “interactive communication is highly accepted in the organization (0.865),” and “the organization’s performance is discussed among the employees (0.901)” (Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013; Nassar, 2017). Empowerment was evaluated using “my organization allows employees to participate in job-related decisions (0.879),” “my superiors encourage me to share ideas for workplace improvement (0.863),” “top management delegates operational authority to the employees (0.898),” and “employees get cooperation from superiors (0.847)” (Boon et al., 2007). OCB was measured by “I willingly assist new colleagues in adjusting to the work environment (0.910),” “I provide innovative suggestions to improve work procedures (0.900),” “I advise my colleagues to solve their problems (0.896),” “I am ready to complete the task of an

absent colleague (0.909),” and “I share my job-related knowledge with my coworkers (0.907)” (Pare & Tremblay, 2007; Lam et al., 2009; Yang, 2012; Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013).

Organizational performance was measured by customer perspective, internal business perspective, pay and benefits perspective, and innovation and technological perspective (Garg & Ma, 2005; Wang et al., 2015). “Customer perspective was evaluated through “customer relations are exemplary in our organization (0.916)”, “customers are delighted with the service provided (0.918)”, “our customers are satisfied with our products/services in comparison to our competitors (0.906)”, and “our organization provides facilities to our customers after sales service (0.915). (Adsit et al., 1996; Raju & Lonial, 2001; Garg & Ma, 2005; Wang et al., 2015). Internal business perspective was measured through “the morale of employees is high in our organization (0.895),” “employees’ productivity in our organization is high (0.871),” “employees are satisfied with the organizational environment (0.888),” and “employee turnover is low in our organization in comparison to the industry average (0.897).” (Garg & Ma, 2005; Wang et al., 2015). Pay and benefits perspective-related questions were “salary is compatible with the performance (0.878),” “good retirement facility is provided to the employees (0.916),” “additional benefits like bonus, gratuity are provided to the employees (0.884),” and “vehicle facility is provided to us (0.871).” (Hartman et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2015). Innovation and technological perspective were measured through “we often introduce new ranges of products or services (0.895),” “we sometimes synchronize the products or services for developing new products or services (0.886),” “we often improve or revise existing products or services (0.898),” and “team cohesiveness is high in the organization (0.891).” (Garg & Ma, 2005; Wang et al., 2015). All questions were measured by a seven-point Likert scale.

Reliability of Variables

The reliability of variables is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Cronbach’s Alpha of Variables

Variables (Constructs)	Cronbach's Alpha
Independent Variable	
Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices	0.851
Selection (SE)	0.905
Training and Development (TD)	0.915
Performance Appraisal (PA)	0.908
Performance-Related Reward (PR)	0.916
Communication (COM)	0.891
Empowerment (EM)	0.901
Mediating Variable	
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)	0.922
Dependent Variable	
Organizational Performance (OP)	0.844
Customer Perspective (CP)	0.934
Internal Business Perspective (IBP)	0.914
Pay and Benefits Perspective (PBP)	0.913
Innovation and Technological Perspective (ITP)	0.917

The all-variables coefficient of Cronbach’s alpha is above 0.70. Thus, all variables are acceptable (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

Convergent and Discriminant Validity

The convergent and discriminant validity-related construct values are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Values of CR, AVE, MSV, Square Root of AVE (Diagonal), and Inter-Construct Correlation (off Diagonal)

	CR	AVE	MSV	PBP	SE	TD	PA	PR	COM	EM	OCB	CP	IBP	ITP
PBP	0.916	0.732	0.023	0.855										
SE	0.907	0.661	0.040	0.124	0.813									
TD	0.919	0.693	0.084	0.134	0.172	0.833								
PA	0.908	0.712	0.040	0.104	0.059	0.173	0.844							
PR	0.915	0.685	0.030	0.101	0.093	0.145	0.037	0.827						
COM	0.895	0.681	0.038	0.128	0.068	0.149	0.061	0.172	0.825					
EM	0.903	0.701	0.074	0.100	0.201	0.228	0.199	0.079	0.188	0.837				
OCB	0.923	0.705	0.106	0.065	0.131	0.289	0.198	0.100	0.160	0.272	0.840			
CP	0.935	0.782	0.097	0.033	0.168	0.241	0.085	0.173	0.196	0.175	0.312	0.884		
IBP	0.914	0.728	0.116	0.151	0.090	0.124	0.084	0.038	0.086	0.190	0.291	0.192	0.853	
ITP	0.918	0.736	0.116	0.107	0.157	0.202	0.104	0.167	0.083	0.161	0.326	0.184	0.340	0.858

All constructs’ composite reliability values (i.e., 0.895 to 0.935) are more than 0.70 (Collier, 2020). Therefore, all constructs are reliable. All construct values of AVE (i.e., 0.661 to 0.782) are greater than 0.5, and each construct’s value of CR is greater than the AVE of the individual construct (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988)”.

Therefore, the result of the test verifies strong evidence of the convergent validity of the constructs.

The individual construct value of AVE (i.e., 0.661 to 0.782) is greater than each construct’s maximum share variance (MSV) (i.e., 0.023 to 0.116), and the square root of AVE values (i.e., 0.823 to 0.884) at the diagonal of the individual construct is higher than the inter-construct correlation values of each off-diagonal construct (Chin, 1998).

Thus, the result of the test confirms strong evidence of the discriminant validity of the constructs.

5. RESULTS

Respondents’ Profile

As 472 respondents have been received from officer-level employees, the respondents’ profile has been revealed in Table 3.

Table 3: Based on gender, marital status, age, and educational level

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	271	57.42
	Female	201	42.58
Marital status	Singal	68	14.41
	Married	404	85.59
Age	Less than 25	21	4.45
	25-34	198	41.95
	35-45	214	45.34
	More than 45	39	8.26
Educational level	Bachelor level	59	12.50
	Master level	399	84.53
	M. Phil	14	2.97

The maximum numbers of male (271, 57.42 percent), married (404, 85.59 percent), 35-45 age group (214, 45.34 percent), and master level (399, 84.53 percent) are in respondents' profiles.

Mediating Effect of Organizational Citizenship Behavior Between HRM Practices and Organizational Performance

Figure 2 shows the model that consists of the first-order construct of organizational citizenship behavior, the second-order construct of HRM practices, and the second-order construct of organizational performance.

Figure 2: Association Among HRMP, OCB and OP

The model exhibits goodness-of-fit with the data in Table 4.

Table 4: Model Fit Measures of HRMP, OCB and OP

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation	References
Chi-square (CMIN)	1899.167			
DF	1067			
Chi-square Associated P Value	0.000			
CMIN/DF	1.780	< 3	Good fit	Byrne, 2010
GFI	0.854	0.80 to 0.90	Acceptable fit	Byrne, 2010
AGFI	0.839	0.80 to 0.90	Acceptable fit	Byrne, 2010
CFI	0.951	> 0.95	Good fit	West et al., 2012
RMSEA	0.041	< 0.05	Good fit	Byrne, 2010

Note: CMIN = Minimum Discrepancy, DF = Degrees of Freedom, P-Value = Probability value, CMIN/DF = Relative Chi-square, GFI = Goodness-of-Fit Index, AGFI = Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation

The relative chi-square (χ^2/df) ratio is 1.780 lower than the suggested threshold (i.e., < 3), showing a good fit (Byrne, 2010). The GFI value is 0.854 with the suggested threshold (i.e., 0.80 to 0.90), indicating an acceptable fit (Byrne, 2010). The AGFI value is 0.839 with the suggested threshold (i.e., 0.80 to 0.90), showing an acceptable fit (Byrne, 2010). The CFI value of 0.951 is greater than the recommended cut-off value of 0.95, indicating a good fit (West et al., 2012). RMSEA value is 0.041 lower than the recommended threshold (i.e., < 0.05), showing a good fit (Byrne, 2010). Thus, all indices ratify the goodness-of-fit with the data.

The path diagram of the mediation test from HRMP through OCB to OP is demonstrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Path Diagram of Mediation Test from HRMP Through OCB to OP

A path exhibits that HRM practices positively and significantly impact OCB ($\beta = 2.592$, t -value = 19.409, P -value = 0.000). Similarly, the B path reveals that OCB positively and significantly influences organizational performance ($\beta = 0.110$, t -value = 13.574, P -value = 0.000). Finally, the C path shows that HRM practices positively and significantly affect organizational performance ($\beta = 1.259$, t -value = 40.048, P -value = 0.000).

The 95% bias-corrected confidence interval for the indirect impact is calculated using the bootstrapping approach (Collier, 2020). According to Taylor et al. (2008), unstandardized coefficients should serve as the foundation for the bootstrapping analysis. When the zero value is excluded from the confidence interval, the mediation is substantial (Collier, 2020). Table 5 displays the results of the OCB mediation test between organizational performance and HRM practices.

Table 5: Mediation Test of OCB Using a Bootstrap Analysis with a 95% Confidence Interval

Relationship Path	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Confidence Interval		p-value	Conclusion
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
HRM Practices ---> OP	1.460 (42.008)				0.000	Partial Mediation
HRM Practices ---> OCB---> OP		0.304	0.245	0.375	0.000	

Note: Unstandardized coefficients reported. Values in parenthesis are t-values. Bootstrap sample = 5,000 with replacement.

HRM practices had a positive and significant effect on organizational performance (1.460, t -value = 42.008, p -value = 0.000). Thus, H_1 is accepted. There is no zero between the lower bound and upper bound confidence interval ($0.375 - 0.245 = 0.130$). Thus, this shows a significant indirect effect (Collier, 2020). The p -value of 0.000 at the intersection of HRM practices and organizational performance reveals the two-tailed significance. Therefore, OCB mediates the relationship between HRM practices and organizational performance. So, H_2 is accepted.

Moreover, there is a positive and significant indirect effect of HRM practices on organizational performance ($\beta = 0.304$, p -value = 0.000). Likewise, there is a positive and significant direct impact of HRM practices on organizational performance ($\beta = 1.460$, t -value = 42.008, p -value = 0.000). The indirect and direct effects are significant and show partial mediation (Collier, 2020). Thus, OCB partially mediates the association between HRM practices and organizational performance.

6. DISCUSSION

This study result shows that HRM practices positively and significantly impact OP in Nepalese public financial institutions. This result is consistent with the previous findings that HRM practices positively and significantly impacted OP (Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013; Amin et al., 2014; Farouk et al., 2016; Taamneh et al., 2018; Jaiswal & Kumar, 2020; Ali et al., 2020; Islami, 2021). However, this study result is inconsistent with the finding of

Nawal et al. (2021), who found that HRM practices had an insignificant effect on OP. A universalistic perspective describes that HRM practices are used in all types of organizations and for all types of employees, which leads to superior OP (Delery & Doty, 1996). For that reason, this result supports the universalistic perspective.

This study finding reveals that the association between HRM practices and OP is mediated through OCB in Nepalese public financial institutions. This result is consistent with the former findings that the association between HRM practices and OP was mediated by OCB (Ko & Smith-Walter, 2013; Taamneh et al., 2018). Moreover, this study result is consistent with the prior finding of Sun et al. (2007), who recognized that OCB mediated the relationship between high-performance HR practices and OP. Positive social exchange theory (Blau, 1964) suggested that the relationship between HRM practices and OP may be mediated by employees' work attitudes (such as OCB). Consequently, this study result supports the positive social exchange theory.

7. CONCLUSION

HRM practices manage the employees through skill enhancement programs, performance-based incentives, and an open communication system, which enhance organizational performance. OCB is a prominent factor in Nepalese public financial institutions that strengthens the link between HRM practices and OP. This study claims that organizational citizenship behavior takes a vital role in enhancing the association between HRMP and OP. Managers can also design OCB as a mediator that plays a prominent role in improving the association between HRMP and OP.

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